

Solutions to Promote Open Innovation Models for Enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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Abstract: In the context of Industry 4.0 and the strong development of digital technology, the open innovation model has become a strategic factor that helps businesses enhance competitiveness and adapt to rapid market changes. This paper uses secondary data collection methods, statistics, analysis, and expert methods to introduce the theoretical basis of open innovation, the challenges and opportunities enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City face when applying this model, and the experiences of global enterprises in implementing open innovation. Additionally, the paper surveys the current application of open innovation in local enterprises, thereby proposing a series of solutions such as enhancing collaboration between businesses and research institutes, promoting connections with the startup ecosystem, and supporting policies from local authorities. The research results contribute to providing a comprehensive perspective and specific recommendations to promote the open innovation model in Vietnam, particularly in Ho Chi Minh City.

Keywords: *Open Innovation, Enterprises, Ho Chi Minh City, Industry 4.0, Startup Ecosystem, Research Collaboration.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization and industry 4.0, open innovation (OI) is a trend, when the strong development of technology and globalization is changing the way businesses approach innovation. The open innovation (OI) model has been applied by many large enterprises in the world as an important strategy. This article focuses on the OI model, the theoretical basis, the opportunities and challenges that this model brings, how large enterprises have applied this model and succeeded, and how is the current situation of open innovation in Ho Chi Minh City? From there, draw lessons and propose solutions to promote open innovation for businesses in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

A. Concept, Necessity and Necessity of Open Innovation Model

Open innovation is a management model in which enterprises seek and combine ideas and technologies from both inside and outside to develop new products, services, and processes.

The open innovation model, introduced by Henry Chesbrough [1] in 2003, is a model in which enterprises use both internal and external resources to develop new ideas, products and services. Instead of relying solely on internal research and development (R&D) teams, enterprises cooperate with other organizations, enterprises, research

institutes, and even customers to promote the innovation process.

In an increasingly globalized and highly competitive business environment, enterprises find it difficult to use only internal resources for innovation. Leveraging external resources (communities, partners, customers, research institutes, and even competitors) has become an important strategic factor and a necessity, an inevitable trend to help accelerate the process of creativity and innovation. Indeed, the complexity of knowledge and technology makes it impossible for any company to develop all aspects of technology on its own. Chesbrough's (2011) research shows that businesses cannot grasp all scientific and technological advances, so cooperation and knowledge sharing with external partners helps promote creativity. Moreover, according to the Transaction Cost Theory (Coase, 1937)[2], cooperation with external partners can help businesses reduce research and development (R&D) costs. Research by Chesbrough and Vanhaverbeke (2010) demonstrates that collaboration between organizations in innovative projects helps to share costs and risks. At the same time, when businesses expand their innovative capabilities through interaction with external innovative ecosystems, they will help businesses quickly adapt to changes in markets and technology, thereby maintaining competitive advantage.

On the other hand, it can be affirmed that open innovation is an inevitable trend in the era of the 4.0 Industrial Revolution. Because first of all, the development

of digital technology and networks with technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain, and big data has opened up many opportunities for businesses to easily access external knowledge and technology resources. Data-based business models and connection platforms are changing the way companies share and collaborate. The rise of collaboration platforms. Moreover, platforms such as GitHub, Kaggle, or global open innovation networks such as InnoCentive have helped businesses connect with scientists, engineers, and experts from around the world. This not only expands research capabilities but also helps businesses solve complex problems faster. Deloitte's (2020) research shows that 63% of executives believe that open innovation is a vital strategic element for business development in the next decade. Pioneering organizations such as IBM, Siemens and Procter & Gamble have successfully applied this model, thereby creating new products and services, meeting diverse market needs.

B. Henry Chesbrough's Theoretical Model of Open Innovation

Henry Chesbrough proposed that businesses should not limit their creativity and development within internal boundaries, but should expand the use of ideas, technology, and knowledge from both inside and outside the organization. The open innovation model has three main directions: Inbound Open Innovation, Outbound Open Innovation, and Coupled Open Innovation.

➤ Inbound Open Innovation

This model focuses on acquiring ideas, technology, and knowledge from outside to improve the company's products, services, or internal processes. External sources can include business partners, research institutes, suppliers, customers, and even competitors.

Unilever has launched the "Open Innovation Portal" program, inviting scientists, experts, and startups from around the world to contribute ideas and technologies to its product research and development projects. Thanks to that, Unilever can reduce the time and cost of internal R&D processes.

➤ Outbound Open Innovation

In this model, businesses not only focus on developing internal technologies and products but also seek to commercialize, share or license these technologies to other organizations and businesses. The goal is to maximize the value of innovations that businesses have developed but do not use directly.

IBM is a typical example of implementing Outbound Open Innovation. IBM develops many internal software technologies but does not fully utilize them. They have licensed many other companies to use their patents and technologies, thereby creating profits and maintaining an open innovation network.

➤ Coupled Open Innovation

This is a model that combines both Inbound and Outbound Open Innovation. Businesses both receive ideas and knowledge from outside and cooperate with partners for common development and sharing benefits. This model requires close collaboration between stakeholders in the research and development process. Tesla is one of the pioneers in applying the Coupled Open Innovation model. Tesla opens its patents to other companies in the electric vehicle industry, and cooperates with partners such as Panasonic to develop battery technology. This not only strengthens Tesla but also promotes the rapid development of the electric vehicle industry.

C. Practical Applications of Open Innovation in Different Industries

➤ Information Technology Industry

- Inbound Open Innovation: In the information technology industry, software companies often use open-source solutions. Google and Microsoft have actively participated in the open source community, using solutions from the external community to develop and improve their products.
- Outbound Open Innovation: Microsoft is also an example of licensing technology to other companies through the "Microsoft Licensing Program". This allows other companies to use Microsoft technology, while generating a large source of income from licensing.

➤ Automotive Industry

- Coupled Open Innovation: As mentioned, Tesla is a typical example in the automotive industry. Tesla not only opens its patents but also cooperates with partners such as Panasonic and Daimler to develop battery and electric vehicle technologies. This creates a rapidly developing ecosystem for electric vehicles.
- Inbound Open Innovation: BMW has implemented the "BMW Innovation Lab" program, where they invite startups to contribute innovative ideas for technological solutions in the automotive industry. This helps BMW quickly access and develop new technologies without having to invest in R&D itself.

➤ Pharmaceutical And Healthcare

- Inbound Open Innovation: Pharmaceutical companies such as Pfizer and GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) frequently collaborate with research institutes, universities, and medical technology startups. Pfizer has implemented "Centers for Therapeutic Innovation" programs to seek out outside medical inventions to develop new treatments.
- Outbound Open Innovation: Novartis has applied Outbound Open Innovation by licensing biotechnologies that it develops but does not directly use, to facilitate other companies to develop pharmaceuticals.

➤ *Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) Industry*

- Coupled Open Innovation: Procter & Gamble (P&G) with its "Connect + Develop" program is a typical example. They invite researchers, suppliers, and partners to contribute to the product development process. In a collaboration with a nanotechnology company, P&G developed an innovative cleaning product by leveraging external technology.

Thus, Henry Chesbrough's Open Innovation Model has changed the way businesses approach product research and development. From Inbound to Outbound, and especially the Coupled Open Innovation model, businesses in many different industries can take advantage of the benefits of sharing knowledge and technology. This helps reduce R&D costs, increase the speed of innovation, and increase competitiveness in a globalized environment.

III. CURRENT STATUS OF OPEN INNOVATION APPLICATION IN HO CHI MINH CITY IN THE PERIOD OF 2020-2024

Ho Chi Minh City is the largest economic and technological center in Vietnam, home to many businesses from key industries such as information technology, manufacturing, services, finance and real estate. In the period of 2020-2024, innovation becomes an important driving force to promote sustainable development of businesses in the context of globalization and digital transformation.

A. Some Achievements in Open Innovation

Ho Chi Minh City has achieved some important successes in the innovation process in recent years, thanks to the support of the government and the strong development of the startup ecosystem. Here are some typical examples:

First, Ho Chi Minh City has successfully built a dynamic startup ecosystem with more than 2,000 startups operating in various fields, from information technology, fintech, to healthcare and education. The city government has supported this by establishing startup incubators, and organizing events connecting startups with international investors and partners. The city also regularly organizes programs such as Saigon Innovation Hub (SIHUB), which helps support startups and innovation by providing free training and consulting courses (26).

Second, Ho Chi Minh City has initiated a Digital Transformation Program with the goal of turning the city into a leading technology and innovation center in Southeast Asia. The city has implemented many digital transformation projects in the fields of public administration, healthcare, and education. In particular, Ho Chi Minh City's Smart City project aims to build a smart urban management system, including a data center and modern information infrastructure, to help improve management efficiency and quality of life for people (28).

Third, many large enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City have invested heavily in R&D and attracted international partners to develop high-tech products. Vinamilk and Viettel are typical examples of companies that have successfully cooperated internationally and used OI to develop new products, especially in the food and telecommunications sectors. These enterprises have applied advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, and IoT to improve their products and services (25).

Fourth, Ho Chi Minh City has successfully built the Saigon Hi-Tech Park (SHTP), a center that attracts large technology corporations such as Intel, Samsung, and Nidec. These enterprises have made great contributions to the development of technology and knowledge transfer to local companies. SHTP is not only a place where large corporations invest in production technology but also a place to promote R&D activities and develop high-quality human resources in Vietnam (29). On the other hand, Ho Chi Minh City has successfully applied innovation in the field of smart healthcare, with the implementation of electronic medical records and smart hospital management systems. This helps improve the ability to manage and provide medical services, while enhancing the ability to care for the city's people. The application of technology in medical data management not only reduces the burden on hospitals but also increases transparency and efficiency (28).

B. State Policies Supporting Open Innovation [3]

In the period of 2020-2024, the State and the Ho Chi Minh City government have issued many policies to promote innovation and digital transformation. These policies focus on creating favorable conditions for businesses and scientific research organizations to cooperate with each other to promote innovation activities. Some typical policies include:

National innovation program: The Ministry of Science and Technology has implemented the National Innovation Program (NISTPASS), supporting businesses in cooperating with research organizations, universities and startups, promoting the open innovation model.

Science and technology development strategy 2021-2030: The Vietnamese Government has proposed a science and technology development strategy to promote cooperation between businesses and research institutes. The Ho Chi Minh City government. Ho Chi Minh City has placed special emphasis on developing the city into a center for innovative startups and high technology, attracting startups and advanced enterprises from all over the world.

Ho Chi Minh City High-Tech Park (SHTP): The city government has developed the Ho Chi Minh City High-Tech Park into a technology ecosystem with policies to support investment attraction and encourage research cooperation between domestic and foreign enterprises, to promote innovation in advanced technology industries.

National Foundation for Science and Technology Development (NAFOSTED): This fund provides financial support to enterprises participating in scientific research and innovation projects, helping to promote open innovation activities through cooperation with research institutes and international partners.

Ho Chi Minh City Innovation Fund (HCMC Innovation Fund): This fund was established to provide financial support to startups and innovation projects. Many high-tech projects, from artificial intelligence to biotechnology, have received funding from the fund to promote cooperation and joint research.

C. Situation of Enterprises Applying Open Innovation

Technology enterprises: Some large technology enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City such as FPT, VNG, VinAI and TMA Solutions have actively applied the open innovation model, especially Inbound Open Innovation. They seek and cooperate with technology start-ups and universities at home and abroad to accelerate the process of developing new products and improving processes.

Manufacturing industry: In the manufacturing sector, large companies such as Samsung, Intel (located in the Ho

Chi Minh City Hi-Tech Park) have cooperated with many international partners to develop advanced technology, applying Coupled Open Innovation. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Ho Chi Minh City have also begun to realize the need for cooperation in research and development (R&D), but the application of open innovation is still limited due to financial resources and management capacity.

Services and e-commerce: E-commerce businesses such as Tiki, Shopee and fintech platforms in Ho Chi Minh City have also started using the Inbound Open Innovation model to attract and cooperate with external solution providers, such as AI, blockchain and big data processing technology. This helps them increase their competitiveness and optimize their services. Healthcare and pharmaceutical businesses: During the COVID-19 pandemic, pharmaceutical and healthcare companies in Ho Chi Minh City, such as DHG Pharma and Sao Thai Duong, have stepped up their cooperation with research institutes and foreign partners to develop new products and treatments. This is an example of Inbound Open Innovation, where businesses leverage external knowledge to develop products that meet market needs.

Table: Results of Open Innovation at Large Enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City in the Period of 2020-2024

Year	Number of Cooperation with External Partners	Revenue from open Innovation Cooperation (billion VND)	Rate of Successful Projects (%)	Number of Newly Developed Products/Services
2020	45	2,100	65	25
2021	55	2,800	70	30
2022	60	3,500	75	35
2023	68	4,000	78	40
2024	75	4,500	80	45

(Source: Vietnam Science, Technology and Innovation Report)

Fig 1 Chart of Number of Collaborations and Revenue from Open Innovation in Ho Chi Minh City
(Source: Vietnam Science, Technology and Innovation Report)

Below are some specific examples of open innovation collaborations between large enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City and domestic and foreign partners in the period of 2020-2024:

- Cooperation between FPT and Airbus, In the field of technology and aviation, FPT and Airbus have cooperated in developing technology solutions to optimize operations for Airbus. FPT has used artificial intelligence (AI) and big data analytics platforms to develop solutions to support aircraft maintenance management and optimize operational processes. This cooperation helps Airbus optimize aircraft maintenance costs and improve operational efficiency. At the same time, FPT has expanded its experience and technology development capacity on a global scale.
- Cooperation between Vingroup and VinAI with Google, Vingroup and VinAI have cooperated with Google to research and develop self-driving car technology. This project focuses on developing AI algorithms for autonomous vehicles, based on the ability to analyze real-time data from sensors and cameras. This cooperation helps Vingroup take a big step forward in developing self-driving car products and increasing VinAI's research capacity. Vingroup also launches many electric and self-driving car products with more advanced technology in the Vietnamese and international markets.
- Cooperation between Viettel and Ericsson, Viettel has cooperated with Ericsson to develop and deploy 5G network solutions in Vietnam. In this cooperation, Viettel uses advanced technologies from Ericsson to deploy 5G

networks, and at the same time develops 5G-based applications such as IoT and smart solutions for the industry. Thanks to this, Viettel has become one of the first telecommunications enterprises to deploy 5G networks in Vietnam, opening up many new business opportunities in areas such as smart cities, industrial automation, and remote healthcare.

- Cooperation between TMA Solutions and Ho Chi Minh City International University, TMA Solutions, one of the major software companies in Ho Chi Minh City, has cooperated with Ho Chi Minh City International University in researching and developing new technology solutions, especially in the fields of artificial intelligence and big data. Students and lecturers from Ho Chi Minh City International University participate in the research and implementation of practical technology projects at TMA. The project has helped strengthen the connection between academia and businesses, giving students the opportunity to be exposed to new technology and solve practical problems of businesses. TMA Solutions has also developed many new products and solutions based on research from this cooperation.
- Cooperation between Vinamilk and DSM (Netherlands), Vinamilk has cooperated with DSM, a biotechnology and food company from the Netherlands, to develop innovative nutritional milk product lines, applying advanced technology in supplementing micronutrients to improve consumers' health. This cooperation has helped Vinamilk enhance its research and production capacity of products with higher nutritional value, expanding domestic and foreign markets, especially markets with

high quality requirements such as Europe and North America.

- Cooperation between Viettel Software Solutions Joint Stock Company (Viettel Software Solutions - VSS) and Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology, Viettel Software Solutions has cooperated with the Faculty of Information Technology of Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology to develop an information management system and process automation for telecommunications enterprises, aiming to improve data management capabilities and enhance operational efficiency. After 12 months of cooperation, the project has successfully developed a new software solution that improves customer management efficiency by 25% and automates many telecommunications processes that previously required manual intervention. The system has been deployed by Viettel Software Solutions for many customers in the telecommunications industry, helping to save operating costs and improve customer experience. Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology has also achieved many important research results and published scientific papers, while providing internship and job opportunities for students participating in the project.

Open innovation collaborations in Ho Chi Minh City have brought many positive results, helping businesses expand their markets, enhance technological capacity, and access knowledge from international partners. At the same time, these collaborations also promote economic development and bring Vietnam into the global technology supply chain.

IV. STRENGTHS, WEAKNESSES, AND CHALLENGES OF OPEN INNOVATION IN HO CHI MINH CITY

A. Strengths of Applying the Open Innovation Model in Ho Chi Minh City

- Enhance innovation and competitiveness capacity through access to new knowledge and technology, create products and services with high added value; shorten product development time to bring products to market faster and reduce research and development costs, share costs and risks with partners.
- Promote diverse cooperation. The open innovation model promotes cooperation between businesses and domestic and international research organizations. Businesses can take advantage of research capacity from universities and research institutes in Ho Chi Minh City, helping to enhance innovation capacity and create higher quality products.
- Create motivation for innovation in businesses and expand the market. This model promotes innovation from all levels of the enterprise. Employees are encouraged to participate in the innovation process and cooperate with external partners, thereby forming a creative corporate culture. By cooperating with foreign partners, enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City can develop products and services that meet international standards,

thereby expanding the market to other regions such as ASEAN, Europe and the US.

B. Weaknesses in Applying the Open Innovation Model in Ho Chi Minh City

- Difficulties in knowledge management and security. When cooperating with external partners, managing and protecting intellectual property rights (IP) becomes a big challenge. Enterprises face the risk of losing control over technology and innovative ideas, especially in international cooperation. Sharing information and knowledge among partners can lead to security risks. Enterprises need to have clear strategies and mechanisms to ensure that information is not abused by partners.
- Corporate culture is not ready, conservative thinking in management is still strong, lack of management and cooperation skills: Many enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City, especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs), still have traditional corporate culture, are not willing to accept cooperation and sharing with external partners, and do not have enough skills and experience in coordinating and managing cooperation projects with external partners.
- Limited resources, lack of high-quality human resources: To successfully implement the open innovation model, enterprises need a team of highly skilled human resources in areas such as technology, innovation management, and knowledge management. However, the shortage of talent, especially in the technology field, is still a big problem in Ho Chi Minh City; financial difficulties are also a headache for small and medium enterprises that want to innovate openly. Despite support from the government, many businesses still face barriers in accessing funding or support programs. - Technology infrastructure is still incomplete, although Ho Chi Minh City has invested heavily in information technology infrastructure, many businesses still face difficulties in accessing and deploying modern technologies such as AI, IoT and Big Data to serve innovation cooperation.

C. Challenges in Applying the Open Innovation Model in Ho Chi Minh City

- Insufficient Policy Support: There is no clear policy framework for open innovation. Currently, most innovation support policies focus on large enterprises and internal R&D projects. Support for open innovation, especially for SMEs, remains insufficient.
- Lack of Incentives for Collaboration: The legal framework for encouraging businesses to collaborate in innovation is still underdeveloped. Regulations on intellectual property rights and benefit-sharing from collaborative projects are unclear, making businesses hesitant to engage in partnerships.
- Weak Linkages Between Enterprises and Research Institutes: Despite having many large research institutes and universities, Ho Chi Minh City lacks strong connections between these institutions and businesses. Companies struggle to find suitable partners for research and development, leading to ineffective utilization of external knowledge.

- **Limited Culture of Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing:** While open innovation requires close cooperation between partners, many businesses in Ho Chi Minh City remain reluctant to share technology, information, and ideas. A collaborative culture needs to be developed through training programs and support from the government and relevant organizations.

Thus, Applying the open innovation model in Ho Chi Minh City offers many benefits but also presents significant challenges. Businesses need to enhance their collaboration management capabilities, invest in high-quality human resources, and foster an open innovation culture to maximize the advantages of this model. At the same time, the city's government should continue to develop policies that support open innovation, particularly for SMEs, to promote sustainable regional development.

V. SOLUTIONS TO PROMOTE THE OPEN INNOVATION MODEL IN HO CHI MINH CITY BY 2030

To promote the open innovation model in Ho Chi Minh City by 2030, solutions need to focus on improving policy mechanisms, building an innovation ecosystem, developing human resources and supporting technology. Below are some feasible solutions based on the current situation and global trends:

A. Improve Policy Mechanisms, Perfect the Legal Framework for Innovation Cooperation, Establish a Clear Legal Corridor on Intellectual Property, Technology Sharing, and Data Security to Create Transparency and Safety in Cooperation Between Businesses, Research Organizations and Stakeholders.

On the other hand, the state needs to have policies to encourage international cooperation to encourage domestic enterprises to participate in research and development projects with foreign partners through cooperation agreements, expanding the Coupled Open Innovation model. It is necessary to apply corporate income tax exemption policies for enterprises that conduct research and development (R&D) activities through cooperation with external partners. The State needs to increase support through science and technology development funds, such as the Ho Chi Minh City Science and Technology Development Fund, to provide finance for enterprises and research organizations participating in open innovation.

B. Building an Open Innovation Ecosystem, Building Innovation Hubs.

Building innovation hubs in Ho Chi Minh City to concentrate high-tech enterprises, start-ups and research institutes in the same area. This helps to increase knowledge exchange, resource and technology sharing among organizations.

➤ *Connecting Enterprises and Universities:*

Ho Chi Minh City authorities need to promote cooperation programs between enterprises and domestic and international universities to put research results into practice. Universities act as sources of knowledge and technology, while businesses can provide resources and test markets.

➤ *Incubator System.*

Establish innovation incubators, develop startup incubation centers in Ho Chi Minh City, where startups and small and medium-sized enterprises can test new ideas, seek investors, and develop products with financial, legal and expert support from larger organizations.

C. Develop High-Quality Human Resources

Training and improving skills for the workforce: The State and businesses need to coordinate with universities and research institutes to develop training programs on open innovation management, high technology (AI, blockchain, big data) and innovative startups. This helps improve the capacity of the workforce to meet the needs of the high-tech market. It is necessary to promote scholarship programs and student and researcher exchanges between Ho Chi Minh City and countries with developed science and technology, creating conditions for the workforce to access international knowledge and apply it to practice in Vietnam.

On the other hand, attracting domestic and international talent is extremely important. Ho Chi Minh City needs to have preferential policies to attract international experts to work in high-tech fields, while encouraging overseas Vietnamese to return home to contribute to innovation activities. This could include support in visas, income, and working conditions.

D. Developing Supporting Technology Infrastructure

Developing supporting technology infrastructure such as (a) investing in digital technology infrastructure, Big Data systems, 5G networks, and IoT: Ho Chi Minh City. HCM needs to increase investment in big data infrastructure, artificial intelligence (AI), and cloud computing so that businesses can easily use technology resources in the innovation process. (b). Create open innovation connection platforms such as: Building digital platforms, similar to InnoCentive or GitHub, allowing businesses in HCM City to connect with international researchers, startups, and experts to exchange ideas, technologies, and innovative solutions. This will help expand the innovation ecosystem and facilitate closer cooperation. 5.5. Promote international cooperation and global innovation such as Participating in international forums and networks, or Attracting investment from international technology companies to learn and share experiences with advanced countries. The government needs to facilitate businesses to participate in events such as the Innovation Summit or international research cooperation programs, and strengthen cooperation with large technology corporations such as Google, Microsoft, and Intel to bring their research and development (R&D) centers to Ho Chi Minh City. This will not only help Ho Chi Minh City access advanced technology but also create opportunities for domestic businesses to cooperate and learn.

VI. CONCLUSION

To promote the open innovation model in Ho Chi Minh City by 2030, solutions need to focus on improving policy mechanisms, building a supporting ecosystem, investing in human resource development and advanced technology. These solutions will help create favorable conditions for businesses to exploit creative potential, promote international cooperation, and contribute to sustainable growth for the economy of Ho Chi Minh City and the whole country.

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